

A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun

By Natalia Moragas Segura, Universitat de Barcelona

Entry tags: Mesoamerican Religions, Religious Group, Otomanguan, Toltec Religion, Language, Teotihuacan Religions

In the beginnings of the Classical era, the Teotihuacans built two cavities that were used for ritual activities. Around 350 AD They were ritually closed. During the Mazapa stage in Teotihuacan (900-1150 AD), they were partially reused as a burial place.

Date Range: 0 CE - 1150 CE

Region: Teotihuacan valley

Region tags: Basin of Mexico, Mesoamerica, Teotihuacan valley, Mexico

El valle de Teotihuacán se ubica al noreste de la cuenca de México, que en tiempos prehispánicos constituía una de las regiones simbióticas más importantes debido a la diversidad de recursos. El pequeño valle de Teotihuacán cuenta con escasos recursos, no hay fuentes de agua permanente y las tierras para el cultivo son relativamente pobres. Por su altitud, la agricultura en el valle está expuesta permanentemente a las inclemencias del clima. Aproximadamente a 10 kilómetros existen yacimientos de obsidiana gris y a unos 70 kilómetros los yacimientos de la obsidiana verde, de la mejor calidad. Ocupa una posición estratégica en la vía de comunicación con el valle poblano-tlaxcalteca y la costa del Golfo de México.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Morante, Rubén (1996) Los observatorios astronómicos subterráneos ¿ un invento teotihuacano? Sociedad Mexicana de Antropología, México, pp 158-172
- Source 1: Moragas Segura, Natalia (2015) Un conjunto ceremonial subterráneo en Teotihuacan . BAR International Series 2766.

Reference: Morante, Rubén . Evidencias Del Conocimiento Astronómico En Teotihuacan.. Tesis. Doctoral

en Antropología. UNAM, 1996.

– Source 1: Soruco Saenz, Enrique (1985) Una cueva ceremonial en Teotihuacan. Tesis de Licenciatura, ENAH.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– URL de la Fuente 1: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y9ER3v68xSg>

– Descripción de la Fuente 1: Short video realted by Prof. Ruben Cabrera about the Astronomical cave.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Sí

Notes: The city of Teotihuacan was occupied by groups from different cultural areas of Mesoamerica. Some of them settled permanently in the city, forming the so-called ethnic neighborhoods. There is archaeological evidence of specific rituals within these complexes that were linked to their local beliefs. There is no clear evidence of conflicts between religions within the city but there are conflicts that ended with major events involving desacralization of buildings and objects. An example linked to this particular entry refers to the events that ended with the desacralization of the Old Temple of the Feathered Serpent. One hypothesis suggests that this conflict had a political-religious nature and that it may also be related to the closure of the tunnels and the closure of the underground complex.

Reference: López Luján, Leonardo, Laura Filloy, Bárbara Fash, William Fash, and Pilar Hernández . “El Poder De Las Imágenes: esculturas Antropomorfas Y Cultos De Élite En Teotihuacan”. In *Arqueología E Historia Del Centro De México. homenaje a Eduardo Matos Moctezuma.*. México: INAH, 2006.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Theoretically, it can be considered that contact is competitive because resources are limited. This competitiveness does not refer exclusively to systematic violence but it can be considered different levels of violence and coercion accompanied by a religious apparatus.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– I don't know

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Sí

Notes: Episodes of violence are detected in Teotihuacan throughout its history. The most obvious are those linked to the crisis that affected the temple of the Feathered Serpent during the Tlamimilolpa phase and the collapse of the city in the Metepec phase. These episodes are related to the process of dismantling and desacralization as well as fires in buildings linked to political and religious power. In the case of the underground ceremonial complex, a closure process is observed around Late Tlamimilolpa that involves some type of ritual. In part of this area there is a fill composed of large stones that covers a large part of the area. It is unknown if this filling was generated in the classic phase and is part of the desacralization processes or if, on the other hand, it was generated as part of the accommodation of the area in the Coyotlatelco-Mazapa phase.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Probably. One of the main themes of Teotihuacan mural painting is the representation of the elites carrying out activities linked to fertility and their role as those in charge of fertilizing the fields thanks to specific rituals and their connection with the deities. In this context, the repetition of the message is a way of proselytize and recruitment.

Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: In the so-called ethnic neighborhoods it has been found that the Teotihuacanos allowed certain rituals outside their official cults. However, the public display of power would be done under Teotihuacan orthodoxy. However, it is suggested that the level of understanding of religion could be adapted to the status of the individual within his/her community and the function that he/she will develop within it.

Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not possible to know but it could be suggested that in the political and commercial ties with other groups, the weight of the Teotihuacan religion had its importance. An example of this could be the elite material culture found outside the city area.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– I don't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Sí

Notes: In Ancient times, politics and religion are intimately related.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Sí

Notes: It is difficult to define the concept paid by the government in a Teotihuacan sense. However, Teotihuacan was home to full-time specialists who were not directly dedicated to the production of food and/or basic necessities. This implies that priests, artisans, domestic workers... were maintained in some way as a productive part of society. We do not have evident data if they were maintained by the state or by the lineages and family groups to which they belonged. In the case of the underground complex during the classical period, a very important religious function of an astronomical nature linked to the calendar is observed. This type of knowledge is very specialized, which requires specific preparation of a select group of priests. It can be considered that this group was formed and maintained by the elites, either in the form of the state as a whole or under the protection of certain family groups in the city.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no archaeological data that allows us to know this point. However, from a theoretical point of view there is no clear differentiation between the political and the religious for the classic era in Teotihuacan.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: We do not have archaeological evidence to help us understand this phenomenon, although some ideas can be suggested taking into account the complex propaganda corpus that occurs in mural painting and sculpture, for example.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Not apostasia in the in the Christian sense of the terms but there is archaeological evidence that shows rituals of desacralization of objects and intentional closures

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The complex has two stages of occupation. The first corresponds to the classical era when the population reached its peak. We do not have absolute dates for this complex but it is plausible that it is part of the same process that built the cavities to the east of the pyramid of the sun. By analysis of ceramics and stratigraphy, this underground complex closes towards the late Tlamimilolpa.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The second phase of occupation of the underground complex corresponds to the transition between the late Coyotlatelco phase and the Mazapa phase, according to the ceramics associated with the burials. For this moment (850-1150), the estimated population is much smaller, between 30,000 to 20,000 inhabitants in the valley.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 30

Notes: The underground ceremonial complex has restricted access because it is surrounded by a wide wall with a single entrance and exit. This reaffirms the idea that privacy was a necessary element for rituals developed in classical times in which astronomical issues were important. By the post-classical period, it is quite likely that the surrounding built area was in a state of open abandonment.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: It is quite likely that by the classical period, there was a clear hierarchy in the priesthood. The hierarchy would be marked by the cult of a specific religious entity and its influence within the hierarchy of power in the city. However, archaeological evidence is complex to identify and there is still much research to be done in this area of knowledge in Teotihuacan. After the collapse of Teotihuacan, it is suggested that post-collapse societies had a lower level of sociopolitical complexity as a consequence of the breakup of the centralized Teotihuacan state.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: From a theoretical framework it is considered that in this type of hierarchical and stratified societies, the religious leaders would be part of the leading lineages of the city. As an example, the Tepantitla mural shows a supernatural being or an individual assuming a supernatural role accompanied by two members of the upper elite who at that moment exercise a priestly function.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From a theoretical framework it is considered that in this type of hierarchical and stratified societies, the religious leaders would be part of the lineages with power within the city.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: We don't have archaeological data to sustain that idea but some researchers suggested that one of the causes of the fall of Teotihuacan were the delegitimization of the elites and the loss of the faith of their followers. That proposal is related to the relationship of the elites with the supernatural beings.

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: There is no evidence in this place. However, the question of whether or not Teotihuacan had writing is a topic of debate among researchers.

Reference: Helmke, Christopher, and Joseph Nielsen. "Teotihuacan Writing:" 55, no. 2 (September 24, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.34314/v1.v55i2.4607>.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The place is located in the main area of the urban center on Teotihuacan, next To the pyramid of the Sun.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not around the underground complex. However, during the classical period the complex was surrounded by a wide wall with a simple slope that limited the access to the place.

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Not in the Christian sense but seems that teotihuacans have some belief related to Tlalocan.

Reference: López Austin, Alfredo. *Tamoanchan Y Tlalocan*. México: FCE, 1994.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: No evidence of sacrifice has been identified in the excavated burials. However, it must be considered that the area has not been completely excavated and that the osteological analyzes carried out are very basic. One dog was buried related to on body.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Valuable items:

– Sí

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Sí

Notes: Shell and one obsidian pendant.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Sí

Notes: In the 13 excavated burials, associated ceramics from the late Coyotlatelco-Mazapa stages were found.

Are formal burials present:

– Sí

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Sí (especifique): underground burials

Notes: In the northwest part of the second cavity, 13 burials were excavated. They are located in a level of clay soil that corresponds to a level of burials dated by ceramics in the late Coyotlatelco-Mazapa phase.

Reference: Moragas Segura, Natalia. "Entierros Al Sudeste Dela Pirámide Del Sol:proyecto Especial Teotihuacan 1992-94.". In *Prácticas Funerarias En La Ciudad De Los Dioses. Los Enterramientos Humanos En La Antigua Teotihuacan.* México: IIA-UNAM, n.d..

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– El campo lo desconoce

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– El campo lo desconoce

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Mesoamerican cultures use body alteration as part of their cultural beliefs. Teotihuacan is no stranger to these customs, although it does not seem that they have become widespread. In the case of the burials from the post-classical stage of the ceremonial underground complex, one of the individuals had dental mutilation. For Teotihuacan, the association of alterations of the body with specific beliefs is not so clear.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: In general terms, Mesoamerican societies practiced self-sacrifice as part of their rituals. In the Ventilla area, a painting was found depicting an individual practicing self-sacrifice by puncturing his penis. However, we have no evidence in this ceremonial complex.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Notes: In Mesoamerican cultures there is an association between caves and taloques, Tlaloc's assistants, represented in the form of children. Evidence of rituals related to these beliefs has been found in the tunnels in the East of the Pyramid of the Sun.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Sí

Notes: In the Teotihuacan culture there is evidence of cults linked to domestic areas in which incense burners, burning of copal, blood sacrifice, specific types of ceramics and obsidians are identified.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

– A chiefdom

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: Institutionalized care are not present but I think it's more related to family unit.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no institutional public education but, following the Mexica model, it is likely that there was an education according to status and gender. Being the Teotihuacans, a hierarchical society, it is quite plausible to consider that specific training must have occurred among lineages and family groups to prepare young people to act according to their social status and gender. In the case of those who led the rituals, the learning must have been more specific. However, specific buildings for this purpose have not been clearly identified.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: If bureaucracy refers to the existence of a group of specialists and/or activities dedicated to the management of public affairs under the mandate of the power of the ruling elites, a bureaucracy must have existed to manage the complexity of a such huge city like Teotihuacan.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: During the period of growth and splendor of Teotihuacan, relationships were established between different groups. Some type of formal diplomacy must have been developed in the form of pacts, alliances and conflicts.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is suggested that

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Sí

Notes: Water control is important both symbolically and naturally. Around the wall that surrounds the underground complex, a drainage was identified that prevented the area from flooding.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Sí

Notes: It has been mentioned that the San Juan River was a communication route that could be used for the transportation of supplies and construction materials.

Reference: Barba, Luis Alberto, and José Luis Córdova Frunz. *Materiales Y Energía En La Arquitectura De Teotihuacan.*, México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México., 2010.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Theoretically it is possible that transportation infrastructure required other social groups related to other institutions

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: In postclassic times, there is evidence of several types of punishment related to religious or non-religious affairs. For Teotihuacan times, we don't have the same information but it is very possible that a kind of punishment existed for several transgressions of a social well-considered behavior.

Reference: Quezada, Noemí. "Mito Y Género En La Sociedad Mexicana." *Revista De Cultura Nahuatl* 26 (1996): 21-40.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Sí

Notes: The astronomical cave has been interpreted as an underground observatory for solar observation linked to the agricultural calendar.

Reference: Morante, Rubén . Evidencias Del Conocimiento Astronómico En Teotihuacan.. Tesis. Doctoral en Antropología. UNAM, 1996.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Bibliography

General References

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Moragas Segura, Natalia. "Cuevas Ceremoniales En Teotihuacan Durante La Época Clásica". *Boletín Americanista* 48 (1998): 179-95.

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Moragas Segura, Natalia. "Cuevas Ceremoniales En Teotihuacan Durante El Periodo Postclásico.". *Boletín Americanista* 55 (2002): 165-76.

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Moragas Segura. "De Los Hoyos De Dónde Sacaron Las Piedras Para Hacer Montecillos": El Sistema Subterráneo E Teotihuacan". *Fuegia* 1 (2018): 31-43.

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Casares, Orlando. "Del Cielo Al Inframundo: Observatorios Astronómicos Subterráneos De Mesoamérica". *Temas Antropológicos* 39, no. 2 (2017): 105-22.

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Morante, Rubén . Evidencias Del Conocimiento Astronómico En Teotihuacan.. Tesis. Doctoral en Antropología. UNAM, 1996.

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Manzanilla, Linda, Claudia López, and AnnCorinne Freter. "Dating Results from Excavations in Quarry

Tunnels Behind the Pyramid of the Sun at Teotihuacan” 7, no. 2 (1996).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0956536100001450>.

Reference: A subterranean ceremonial complex in the southeast of Teotihuacan's Pyramid of the Sun, Moragas Segura, Natalia. “Del Chicomostoc Al Sepulcro Sagrado Cambio Y Transformación En Los Cultos Subterráneos En El Altiplano Central”. In *Construcción Social Y Cultural Del Poder En Las Américas*. Barcelona: Universitat de Barcelona-Casa América Barcelona., 2015.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Sí, Barba, Luis Alberto, and José Luis Córdova Frunz. *Materiales Y Energía En La Arquitectura De Teotihuacan*., México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México., 2010.

Reference: Source 1: Moragas Segura, Natalia (2015) Un conjunto ceremonial subterráneo en Teotihuacan . BAR International Series 2766., Morante, Rubén . *Evidencias Del Conocimiento Astronómico En Teotihuacan*.. Tesis. Doctoral en Antropología. UNAM, 1996. ,

Reference: No, Helmke, Christopher, and Joseph Nielsen. “Teotihuacan Writing:” 55, no. 2 (September 24, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.34314/vl.v55i2.4607>.

Reference: El campo lo desconoce, Quezada, Noemí. “Mito Y Género En La Sociedad Mexica.”. *Revista De Cultura Nahuatl* 26 (1996): 21-40.

Reference: Sí, López Luján, Leonardo, Laura Filloy, Bárbara Fash, William Fash, and Pilar Hernández . “El Poder De Las Imágenes:esculturas Antropomorfas Y Cultos De Élite En Teotihuacan”. In *Arqueología E Historia Del Centro De México.homenaje a Eduardo Matos Moctezuma*.. México: INAH, 2006.

Reference: El campo lo desconoce, López Austin, Alfredo. *Tamoanchan Y Tlalocan*. México: FCE, 1994.

Reference: Sí (especifique): underground burials, Moragas Segura, Natalia. “Entierros Al Sudeste Dela Pirámide Del Sol:proyecto Especial Teotihuacan 1992-94.”. In *Prácticas Funerarias En La Ciudad De Los Dioses. Los Enterramientos Humanos En La Antigua Teotihuacan*.. México: IIA-UNAM, n.d..